

Mushroom Production in Forests

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Shiitake mushroom production in agroforestry systems of Galicia (NW Spain)

European mushroom cultivation represents a vital agricultural sector that merges tradition with innovation. Producing around 1 million tonnes each year, mushroom cultivation provides a substantial income for thousands of farmers while offering a nutritious and sustainable food source. Mushroom production can be included in any agroforestry system with suitable conditions, being the shiitake mushroom the most widely cultivated mushroom for temperate agroforestry. Moreover, shiitake mushrooms have the greatest commercial demand among all mushroom varieties. Traditionally, shiitake cultivation has been practised on logs and is consistently successful when grown outdoors. Almost any deciduous tree that retains its bark for several years can be used to cultivate shiitake on logs. For inoculation, logs should be drilled longitudinally along the trunk every 10–15 cm and filled with shiitake mushroom mycelium. The holes are arranged in staggered rows, with each row spaced approximately 5–10 cm apart from the previous one. The holes are then sealed with natural wax, and the ends of the logs are covered with plastic film to prevent contamination and help retain moisture within the log. The logs are kept in a cool, humid place to promote incubation, a process that takes about 12 months. Before initiating shiitake mushroom production and to trigger spore formation, the logs are submerged in spring water at 14.5°C for 48 hours. This process rapidly cools and hydrates the logs, simulating the environmental conditions of autumn. Then, the logs can be placed in agroforestry areas, stacked in a crisscross tower formation to improve aeration and support optimal mushroom growth. In general, under adequate conditions of temperature and humidity, shiitake mushroom production starts one month after the log installation in the field.

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